

Progressive Feature Enrichment for Ligand Binding-Site Prediction: From Tabular Chemistry to Protein Language Models

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Author
Maximilian Hageneder,
BSc
11942708

Submission
**Institute for Machine
Learning**

Thesis Supervisor
Univ.-Prof. Mag. Dr. **Günter
Klambauer**

Assistant Thesis
Supervisor
Florian Sestak, MSc

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Abstract

An early step in structure-based drug discovery is the identification of ligand-binding-sites on protein structures. Existing approaches range from geometric and energetic heuristics to supervised learning pipelines on handcrafted structural descriptors and learned representations from large protein sequence corpora. However, the relative contribution of local physico-chemistry, sequence-derived information, and spatial context is rarely quantified under controlled comparisons.

This thesis studies ligand-binding-site prediction through a staged ablation design. We begin by reproducing an established solvent-accessible-surface baseline in a modern Python framework. We then test whether modern tabular learners can match or exceed the original random-forest formulation when trained on identical handcrafted descriptors. Next, we progressively enrich the representation. We first add residue-level context from protein language models. We then model local surface neighbourhoods with a transformer-style kNN-restricted attention mechanism. Across benchmarks, these information sources act complementarily. Handcrafted geometric descriptors provide a strong structural prior, sequence-derived embeddings highlight functionally constrained regions, and neighbourhood aggregation sharpens spatially coherent pocket boundaries. The resulting fusion model substantially improves upon the handcrafted baseline on challenging apo targets. By releasing the full pipeline and evaluation protocol as open-source, this work provides a reproducible framework for analysing and improving binding-site predictors for structure-based drug discovery.

Kurzfassung

Ein früher Schritt in der strukturbasierten Wirkstoffforschung ist die Identifizierung von Ligandenbindungsstellen auf Proteinstrukturen. Bestehende Ansätze reichen von geometrischen und energetischen Heuristiken bis hin zu überwachten Lernverfahren, die auf manuell definierten Strukturdeskriptoren sowie auf gelernten Repräsentationen aus großen Proteinsequenz-Korpora basieren. Der relative Beitrag von lokalen physikochemischen Eigenschaften, sequenzbasierten Signalen und räumlichem Kontext wird in kontrollierten Vergleichen jedoch nur selten quantifiziert.

Diese Arbeit untersucht die Vorhersage von Ligandenbindungsstellen anhand einer gestuften Ablationsstudie. Zunächst reproduzieren wir eine etablierte Baseline, die auf der lösungsmittelzugänglichen Oberfläche (SAS) basiert, in einem modernen Python-Framework. Anschließend prüfen wir, ob moderne Lernverfahren für tabellarische Daten die ursprüngliche Random-Forest-Formulierung bei Verwendung identischer, manuell definierter Deskriptoren erreichen oder übertreffen können. Danach erweitern wir die Repräsentation schrittweise. Zuerst fügen wir Kontext auf Aminosäureebene aus Protein-Sprachmodellen hinzu. Anschließend modellieren wir lokale Oberflächennachbarschaften mit einem Transformer-ähnlichen, durch k-nächste-Nachbarn (kNN) beschränkten Aufmerksamkeitsmechanismus (Attention).

Über alle Benchmarks hinweg liefern diese Informationsquellen komplementäre Signale. Manuell definierte geometrische Deskriptoren stellen ein starkes strukturelles Vorwissen bereit, sequenzbasierte Einbettungen heben funktionell konservierte Regionen hervor und die Aggregation von Nachbarschaftsinformationen präzisiert die Grenzen räumlich zusammenhängender Bindungstaschen. Das resultierende Fusionsmodell übertrifft die bisherige Baseline deutlich, insbesondere bei anspruchsvollen Apo-Strukturen. Durch die Veröffentlichung der vollständigen Pipeline und des Evaluationsprotokolls als Open-Source schafft diese Arbeit ein reproduzierbares Rahmenwerk zur Analyse und Weiterentwicklung von Bindungsstellenprädiktoren für die strukturbasierte Wirkstoffforschung.

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List of Acronyms

AUPRC	Area Under Precision-Recall Curve
AUROC	Area Under Receiver Operating Characteristic
BU48	Bound/Unbound benchmark of 48 apo/holo-protein pairs
CHEN11	Chen 2011 holo-protein dataset
CI	Confidence Interval
CLI	Command Line Interface
DCC	Distance from binding-site centre to predicted-cluster centre
DCA	Distance from predicted-cluster centre to nearest ligand atom
DDP	Distributed Data Parallel (PyTorch)
ESM2	Evolutionary Scale Modeling 2 (protein language-model)
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format 5
IoU	Intersection over Union
kNN	k-Nearest Neighbours
P2Rank	Ligand binding-site predictor using random forests
PyMOL	PyMOL Molecular Graphics System
SAS	Solvent-Accessible Surface
SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique
SWA	Stochastic Weight Averaging
TabNet	Attentive Interpretable Tabular Learning

Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter motivates ligand-binding-site prediction as a problem in structure-based drug discovery, reviews the relevant literature, and identifies the research gaps that motivate the staged study conducted in the remainder of this thesis.

1.1 Motivation and Context

Structure-based drug discovery (SBDD) benefits from identifying ligandable regions on protein surfaces before committing to computationally expensive docking simulations or costly wet-lab validation campaigns. The standard drug discovery pipeline (Figure 1.1) illustrates the role of target identification and hit discovery early in the process. In structure-based settings where a target structure is available, binding-site prediction can prioritise plausible binding regions for structure-based screening.

Figure 1.1: The standard drug discovery pipeline (Zhang et al., 2022). In structure-based settings, binding-site prediction can support hit discovery by prioritising plausible binding regions for docking and downstream optimisation.

Predicting binding-sites from protein structure alone, even without knowledge of ligand identity, can accelerate hit discovery, prioritise regions for docking, and guide structure-informed experimental design such as mutagenesis

studies (Kozakov et al., 2015). Consequently, binding-site prediction has attracted sustained attention across structural biology, cheminformatics, and machine learning communities over the past two decades.

It is crucial to distinguish binding-site prediction from molecular docking. While docking aims to predict the pose and binding affinity of a *specific* ligand within a candidate pocket, binding-site prediction identifies the pocket itself, the “lock” into which a potential “key” might fit (Figure 1.2). This distinction matters because docking algorithms often fail if the search space is not constrained to a likely binding region. While the lock-and-key analogy is illustrative, many protein–ligand interactions follow induced-fit or conformational-selection mechanisms, making protein flexibility an important confounder for static-structure pipelines.

Figure 1.2: The Lock and Key complementarity model (Nagwa, 2024). Binding-site prediction identifies the geometric and chemical “lock” (protein pocket) that complements the “key” (ligand), a prerequisite for specific molecular recognition.

Binding sites are further categorized into orthosteric and allosteric sites. The orthosteric site is the primary active site where the endogenous ligand binds to carry out the protein’s function. Allosteric sites are spatially distinct regions that regulate protein activity through conformational changes (Figure 1.3). For example, aspirin inhibits cyclooxygenase enzymes and thereby reduces prostaglandin synthesis (Vane, 1971). Identifying such sites is a foundational step in rational drug design.

Figure 1.3: Orthosteric versus allosteric inhibition mechanisms (Vainchenker et al., 2018). Allosteric inhibitors (**left**) bind to a distal site, inducing conformational changes that render the active site non-functional. Orthosteric inhibitors (**right**) compete directly with the substrate for the active site. Detecting both types of pockets is essential for comprehensive druggability assessment.

A fundamental challenge in this domain is the reliance on static structural data. The *Protein Data Bank* (PDB) serves as the primary global repository for 3D

structural data of large biological molecules, providing the structural snapshots used to train predictive models (Berman et al., 2000). However, proteins are inherently dynamic entities, existing as ensembles of conformations rather than rigid structures. Most machine learning models, including the ones developed in this thesis, are trained on static experimental structures, which may represent only one of many functional states. This “snapshot bias” means that cryptic pockets (Cimermancic et al., 2016) (binding-sites that only open during specific conformational excursions) may be missed if the static-structure captures a closed state.

Early approaches to pocket detection emphasised geometric properties: algorithms such as LIGSITE (Huang and Schroeder, 2006), SURFNET (Laskowski, 1995), and Fpocket (Le Guilloux et al., 2009) identify cavities based on surface geometry and local packing. In particular, Fpocket clusters *alpha spheres* derived from Voronoi-based geometric constructions to delineate putative pockets. These methods are computationally efficient and interpretable, but can produce false positives by flagging concave regions that are not chemically favourable for ligand-binding.

To address these limitations, *Ligand binding-site predictor using random forests* (P2Rank) (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018) reframed binding-site detection as a supervised ligandability classification problem on *solvent-accessible surface* (SAS) points. Instead of relying solely on geometry, P2Rank computes a 35-dimensional physicochemical descriptor vector for each SAS point and trains a random-forest classifier. The resulting predictor achieved strong performance on multiple benchmarks. However, P2Rank’s implementation is tightly integrated into a Java ecosystem, and the random-forest has not been systematically compared against modern tabular learners under identical preprocessing and feature definitions.

Concurrently, *protein language models* (PLMs) such as ESM2 (Z. Lin et al., 2023) have demonstrated the capacity to capture sequence-derived signals that correlate with structure and function. Recent work has begun exploring the integration of PLM embeddings into structure-based tasks, but often without isolating the marginal contribution of sequence-derived embeddings relative to strong geometric baselines.

A third consideration is spatial cooperativity: ligand-binding-sites are rarely characterised by isolated high-scoring points, but rather by contiguous patches on the surface. Traditional point-wise classifiers treat each SAS location independently. Recent advances in attention mechanisms offer natural frameworks for modelling such dependencies via neighbourhood aggregation.

This thesis addresses these gaps by constructing a modular, reproducible pipeline that systematically integrates geometric, sequence-derived, and relational information for binding-site prediction.

Code availability. The complete implementation (data generation, feature-extraction, training, and evaluation) is available at github.com/lal3lu03/PocketNet.

1.2 Literature Review

This section situates our approach within the broader landscape of ligand-binding-site prediction. We first review geometry-driven cavity detectors and surface-point ensemble methods, then discuss deep neural pipelines based on voxelised grids and language-enhanced geometric deep learning. We conclude with a comparative overview of representative methods and a discussion of evaluation paradigms.

1.2.1 Geometry-Driven Pocket Detection

Early computational approaches infer binding-sites by analysing geometric characteristics of the protein surface. Tools such as Fpocket (Le Guilloux et al., 2009) cluster alpha spheres to delineate cavities, whereas LIGSITEcsc extends grid-based surface scanning with conservation signals to stabilise predictions across homologues (Huang and Schroeder, 2006). These algorithms deliver rapid screening and offer intuitive interpretations, yet their reliance on primarily structural cues limits sensitivity when apo and holo conformations diverge.

1.2.2 Surface-Point Learning and Ensemble Methods

P2Rank (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018) reframed pocket detection as a supervised learning problem on SAS points, pairing a random-forest with handcrafted descriptors that encode local hydrophobicity, protrusion, and residue composition. The ensemble formulation achieves strong accuracy while remaining lightweight, but downstream practitioners face a Java-centric implementation and limited guidance on integrating richer molecular context or alternative learners within a reproducible evaluation protocol.

1.2.3 Deep Neural Pipelines

Three-dimensional convolutional networks have been applied to voxelised grids around candidate pockets. DeepSite (Jiménez et al., 2017) introduced the idea of learning volumetric filters over atom-type density maps, while DeepPocket (Aggarwal et al., 2021) extended the paradigm with U-Net-inspired segmentation heads that delineate cavity shape more precisely. DeepPocket combines Fpocket’s geometric preselection with CNN refinement, achieving competitive success rates on standard benchmarks (Aggarwal et al., 2021). The dual-stage approach balances efficiency and precision: Fpocket’s alpha-sphere clustering rapidly filters candidate regions, while the CNN processes voxelised neighbourhoods to predict ligandability distributions.

Despite competitive performance on established benchmarks, voxelised representations incur substantial memory and computational costs. Dense 3D grids scale cubically with spatial resolution, limiting throughput in high-volume screening scenarios. Furthermore, reliance on geometric preselection inherits sensitivity to cavity-detection thresholds, potentially missing shallow or

solvent-exposed binding-sites. In contrast, the SAS-point formulation explored in this thesis operates directly on surface discretisations, avoiding volumetric overhead while retaining fine-grained spatial resolution.

1.2.4 Protein Language Models and Geometric Deep Learning

Protein language models such as ESM2 (Z. Lin et al., 2023) encode sequence-derived context into high-dimensional embeddings that correlate with functional annotations, capturing patterns of conservation and co-evolution from large protein sequence corpora. ESM2 employs a transformer architecture trained via masked language modelling on UniRef datasets, yielding per-residue representations that capture structural and functional constraints without explicit 3D input.

In parallel, geometric deep learning has introduced equivariant graph neural networks (GNNs) that process protein structures directly. VN-EGNN (Sestak et al., 2024) extends EGNN-style $E(3)$ -equivariant message passing with a set of *virtual nodes* whose *coordinates* are trained to converge toward binding-site centres. The method couples residue-level segmentation with an explicit binding-site-centre objective and motivates virtual nodes as a mechanism to mitigate *oversquashing* in deep message passing (Sestak et al., 2024). Virtual nodes are initialised on a Fibonacci sphere around the protein and are connected to residue nodes ($C\alpha$ graph) but not to each other (Sestak et al., 2024). Importantly, VN-EGNN is primarily a *geometric* model, but its full variant uses *pre-trained ESM-2 embeddings* as initial residue node features, and the paper reports ablations with and without ESM features (Sestak et al., 2024). On the COACH₄20 benchmark, VN-EGNN improves localisation under DCC/DCA success criteria compared to geometry-only baselines (Sestak et al., 2024).

However, few studies systematically quantify how PLM features interact with traditional SAS descriptors or measure their incremental value over robust tabular baselines within a fixed SAS-point pipeline. Existing comparisons often conflate architecture differences (CNNs versus GNNs and voxel grids versus point clouds) with representational differences (handcrafted descriptors versus learned embeddings), obscuring the marginal contribution of language-model context. This thesis addresses that gap by holding the SAS-point pipeline constant and progressively enriching the feature set, isolating the effects of ESM2 embeddings and neighbourhood aggregation from confounding factors such as model family and preprocessing.

1.2.5 Comparative Overview

Representative methods span geometry-driven heuristics (Fpocket, LIGSITE_{csc}), supervised SAS-point ensembles (P2Rank), voxel-based CNN pipelines (DeepPocket), and equivariant GNNs with virtual nodes (VN-EGNN). Fpocket and LIGSITE_{csc} offer rapid screening from alpha spheres and surface scanning but omit richer chemical cues. P2Rank learns from 35-dimensional SAS descriptors with random forests, balancing accuracy and interpretability. DeepPocket stacks Fpocket preselection with a U-Net to achieve high top- n success, trading compute for precision. VN-EGNN extends equivariant residue-graph message passing with virtual nodes that explicitly predict

binding-site centres and reports further gains when using pre-trained ESM-2 residue embeddings as node features (with ablations without ESM) (Sestak et al., 2024). This thesis keeps the SAS formulation and progressively enriches representations with TabNet, ESM2 embeddings, and transformer-style kNN aggregation, reporting IoU on the BU48 benchmark under a consistent data generation and evaluation protocol.

1.2.6 Evaluation Paradigms: Point-Wise vs. Pocket-Level Metrics

Binding-site prediction methods are typically evaluated under two complementary paradigms: point-wise overlap metrics and pocket-level success rates. Understanding the trade-offs between these approaches is critical for interpreting experimental results and comparing methods across studies.

Point-wise metrics (IoU, precision, recall, AUPRC) measure the spatial overlap between predicted and ground-truth binding-site points at the SAS level. In this thesis, intersection-over-union is defined as

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{|P \cap G|}{|P \cup G|},$$

where P and G denote the predicted and ground-truth sets of labelled SAS points, respectively. These metrics directly quantify the model’s ability to identify ligandable surface regions at fine granularity, making them sensitive to local accuracy and well-suited for methods that operate on continuous surface representations (SAS points, voxel grids). Point-wise evaluation penalises both over-prediction (false positives) and under-prediction (false negatives), providing a deterministic assessment of segmentation quality.

Pocket-level metrics ($\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$, DCC, DCA, top- n success) cluster predictions into discrete pockets and evaluate whether at least one predicted pocket overlaps with the ground-truth binding-site. *Distance from Centre of the binding-site to Centre of the prediction cluster* (DCC) and *Distance from Centre of the prediction cluster to the nearest Atom in the binding-site* (DCA) (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018) quantify the spatial proximity of predicted pockets to ligand-binding regions. Top- n success rates report the fraction of proteins for which at least one of the top n ranked pockets intersects the true binding-site, typically with $n \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

Pocket-level evaluation is more forgiving of small localisation errors and better aligns with downstream docking workflows, where identifying a plausible binding region is often sufficient even if the predicted pocket does not perfectly match the ligand footprint. However, converting point-wise predictions into discrete pockets requires a clustering step such as *Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise* (DBSCAN) (Ester et al., 1996), which introduces additional hyperparameters (e.g., ϵ and min_samples) and post-processing choices (score thresholding, non-maximum suppression). These design choices can materially affect pocket counts and success rates, making it harder to attribute changes in performance to the underlying model alone.

To minimise this confounding effect, we take three steps. First, we keep DBSCAN and post-processing parameters fixed across all Stage III runs. Second, we report the chosen values explicitly. Third, we treat pocket-level metrics as a supplementary evaluation alongside deterministic SAS-point metrics that do not require clustering.

This thesis adopts point-wise IoU_{SAS} as the primary metric to maintain simplicity and reproducibility, avoiding the confounding effects of clustering algorithms. Stratified error analyses (Section 4.5) provide additional insight into per-protein performance. Future work should bridge these paradigms by developing end-to-end metrics that reflect real-world screening utility while preserving deterministic evaluation (Aggarwal et al., 2021; Sestak et al., 2024).

1.3 Research Gap and Open Questions

Despite extensive prior work, three critical gaps persist:

Gap 1: Lack of Modular Baselines. Most published methods entangle feature engineering, model architecture, and training protocols, making it difficult to isolate the source of improvements. P2Rank’s success could be due to its careful feature design, the ensemble of random forests, or the quality of its training data, yet few studies compare modern learners (e.g., XGBoost, TabNet, neural networks) on identical P2Rank-style features under matched pipelines. Without such controlled comparisons, practitioners cannot confidently choose between tree ensembles and deep tabular models for SAS descriptors.

Gap 2: Unclear Marginal Benefit of PLMs. While protein language models have transformed sequence-based tasks, their incremental value for geometry-centric problems like pocket prediction depends on the strength of the geometric baseline and the evaluation protocol. Language-enhanced geometric models report improved localisation on established benchmarks when using ESM-derived residue embeddings, with ablations indicating non-trivial contributions from these sequence-derived features (Sestak et al., 2024). However, controlled studies that isolate the marginal benefit of PLM embeddings over strong SAS-descriptor baselines within a fixed surface-point pipeline remain limited.

Gap 3: Insufficient Attention to Spatial Cooperativity. Nearly all SAS-based methods treat each surface-point independently, despite biological evidence that ligands bind to contiguous patches with coordinated chemistry. Graph neural networks address this for residue-level graphs, but direct application of attention mechanisms to dense SAS discretisations remains comparatively underexplored. Furthermore, existing methods rarely analyse how single-point descriptors and neighbourhood aggregation interact in an interpretable, calibrated manner.

Taken together, these gaps motivate a staged study of solvent-accessible-surface-based ligand-binding-site prediction that progressively enriches a strong P2Rank-style baseline with protein language-model embeddings and spatial neighbourhood aggregation.

1.4 Thesis Outline

The remainder of this thesis is structured as follows.

Chapter 1 (Introduction). This chapter motivates ligand-binding-site prediction, reviews the relevant literature, and identifies the research gaps.

Chapter 2 (Data and Problem Formulation). This chapter details the datasets (CHEN11, BU48), describes the data generation process (SAS sampling, labelling), and formalises the research questions and hypotheses.

Chapter 3 (Methodology and Feature Design). This chapter describes the feature design, including P2Rank-style descriptors, ESM2 embeddings, and the transformer-based neighbourhood aggregation architecture.

Chapter 4 (Results). This chapter presents quantitative results for all stages, including SAS-point and pocket-level metrics, and compares performance across learner families and feature sets.

Chapter 5 (Discussion). This chapter interprets the findings, discusses trade-offs and limitations, and outlines future directions.

Appendices. The appendices provide supplementary details on descriptors, hyperparameters, and software artefacts.

Chapter 2

Data and Problem Formulation

This chapter details the datasets used for training and evaluation, describes the data generation process, and formalises the prediction task, research questions, and hypotheses that guide this study.

2.1 Datasets

We curate two complementary datasets to ground the study in established ligandability benchmarks.

CHEN11. The CHEN11 benchmark introduced by Chen et al. (K. Chen et al., 2011) comprises 251 non-redundant protein targets and 476 bound ligands. In our preprocessing, this benchmark expands to 788 holo-protein-ligand complexes (multiple structures and/or ligands per target after filtering and chain resolution), yielding approximately 4.72 million SAS points. We split CHEN11 into training and validation subsets using an 80/20 grouped split (seed 42), ensuring that all complexes associated with the same target identifier are assigned to the same fold. This results in 3.89M training points and 0.831M validation points.

BU48. The B48/U48 benchmark provides 48 proteins for which both a bound (holo) and unbound (apo) structure is available (Huang and Schroeder, 2006; Krivák and Hoksza, 2018). We use the apo structures (U48) as a completely held-out test-set to stress generalisation to conformational shifts. After preprocessing, BU48 contributes 216,834 SAS points (apo conformations). For labelling, each apo structure is aligned to its paired holo structure before transferring ligand-proximity labels (Section 2.2).

Structure parsing and filtering. *Protein Data Bank* (PDB) files are parsed with Biopython (Cock et al., 2009). We retain the first model, discard crystallographic waters, and resolve alternate locations by selecting the highest-occupancy conformer (ties broken deterministically). Atoms with missing coordinates are ignored rather than modelled to avoid injecting speculative geometry. Standard amino-acid residues define the receptor. Hetero residues are considered only for identifying the annotated functional ligand used in labelling.

2.2 Data Generation

Following the surface-point formulation popularised by P2Rank (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018), we represent each structure by a set of solvent-accessible surface (SAS) points. We approximate the SAS using the Shrake–Rupley algorithm (Shrake and Rupley, 1973) with a 1.6 \AA probe radius. Across CHEN11 and BU48, this yields approximately 4.94 million SAS points.

Figure 2.1: Representative views from the recreated SAS pipeline, shown in a consistent orientation. The panels progress from protein fold to surface chemistry, model-derived ligandability, and the final SAS-point discretisation used for point-wise prediction.

Labelling. For holo complexes, a SAS point is labelled positive if at least one heavy atom of the bound ligand falls within 6 \AA of the point. For BU48 (apo test structures), we first superpose apo onto holo via backbone least-squares alignment and then apply the same distance-based labelling using the holo lig-

and coordinates. The resulting class-imbalance is severe, with approximately **2.55% positive samples** across the combined dataset. All points originating from the same structure are kept together in the same split to prevent leakage between training and evaluation.

2.3 Problem Formulation

We cast ligand-binding-site prediction as point-wise binary classification (and later, calibrated probability estimation) over SAS discretisations.

For a protein structure, let $\mathcal{P} = \{p_i\}_{i=1}^N$ denote SAS points with associated feature vectors $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and binary labels $\{y_i\}_{i=1}^N$, where $y_i = 1$ indicates ligand-proximal surface and $y_i = 0$ otherwise. The goal is to learn a function f_θ that maps features (and, depending on the stage, neighbourhood context) to ligandability scores:

$$\hat{y}_i = f_\theta(x_i, \mathcal{N}(i)) \in [0, 1],$$

where $\mathcal{N}(i)$ denotes optional spatial neighbourhood information (disabled in the baseline, enabled in later stages).

Model selection is performed on the CHEN11 validation split. Final generalisation is reported on BU48 (apo) to explicitly evaluate robustness under conformational shift.

2.4 Research Questions and Hypotheses

The central research question guiding this thesis is:

To what extent can progressive feature enrichment, spanning from physicochemical descriptors through protein language-model embeddings to spatial neighbourhood aggregation, improve ligand-binding-site prediction?

We decompose this question into three specific research questions:

- **RQ1:** Can modern tabular learning improve upon random-forest baselines when trained on identical SAS descriptors?
- **RQ2:** Does adding protein language-model features (ESM2 embeddings) provide consistent gains over geometric and physicochemical descriptors?
- **RQ3:** Does modelling spatial cooperativity via neighbourhood aggregation further refine predictions beyond point-wise classification?

These questions are paired with testable hypotheses:

- **H1:** A modern tabular learner (e.g., TabNet) outperforms a random-forest when trained on the same handcrafted SAS descriptors.
- **H2:** Adding ESM2 embeddings improves generalisation, particularly on BU48 where apo/holo shifts reduce the reliability of purely geometric cues.
- **H3:** Neighbourhood aggregation improves boundary delineation and reduces isolated false positives by exploiting spatial continuity of binding patches.

To answer these questions, we pursue five specific contributions (C1–C5), detailed in Appendix A. These include a reproducible open-source SAS pipeline, a systematic tabular learning benchmark, quantified ESM2 integration, transformer-based neighbourhood aggregation, and a reproducible evaluation framework.

Chapter 3

Methodology and Feature Design

This chapter describes the feature engineering and model architectures used in this study. We detail the construction of P2Rank-style tabular descriptors, the integration of protein language-model embeddings, and the transformer-based neighbourhood aggregation mechanism.

3.1 P2Rank-Derived Physicochemical Descriptors

Each SAS point receives a 35-dimensional descriptor vector that reproduces the physicochemical surface descriptors distributed with P2Rank (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018). Following the P2Rank formulation, descriptors summarise the local chemical neighbourhood around each surface-point via distance-weighted aggregation over nearby protein atoms (using a fixed cut-off neighbourhood) and additional geometric summary statistics, including the protrusion feature that proxies “buriedness” (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018). These descriptors are designed to capture properties spanning multiple levels of protein organisation (Figure 3.1), from residue composition and hydrophathy to local packing and surface shape.

Figure 3.1: Hierarchy of protein structural levels (Toppr, 2024). The 35-dimensional descriptor set encodes local chemistry (residue composition, hydrophathy, donor/acceptor patterns) together with geometric cues (e.g., protrusion and packing proxies), yielding a multi-scale representation of the binding environment.

For readability, we group the 35 descriptors into six thematic blocks:

1. **Local surface and packing proxies:** summary statistics that reflect local surface density and atomic crowding (geometric texture and “buriedness”).
2. **Flexibility proxy:** neighbourhood-aggregated B-factor statistics, providing a local indicator of structural disorder and mobility.
3. **Residue composition:** amino-acid type frequencies in the local neighbourhood, capturing coarse biochemical context and motif-like patterns.
4. **Hydropathy:** neighbourhood-aggregated Kyte–Doolittle hydropathy (Kyte and Doolittle, 1982), reflecting local polarity/hydrophobicity.
5. **Environment descriptors (volsite-style):** counts or weighted aggregates of atom categories (e.g., aromatic, cationic, anionic, hydrophobic, H-bond donor/acceptor), approximating interaction-relevant chemistry without explicit force-field calculations.
6. **Protrusion and hydrophobicity indices:** protrusion-style measures of exposure/packing and neighbourhood hydrophobicity terms that refine the coarse hydropathy signal.

Figure 3.2: Hydrogen bonding as a key secondary interaction (Wikimedia Commons contributors, 2024). Environment descriptors approximate the presence of hydrogen-bond donor/acceptor patterns that contribute to ligand-binding affinity and specificity.

Descriptor computation is implemented in NumPy/SciPy (Harris et al., 2020; Virtanen et al., 2020) with residue-level caching to avoid redundant traversals. All features are computed deterministically from PDB coordinates. Missing B-factors (affecting < 2% of residues) are replaced with the chain median to avoid introducing artificial outliers, and alternate locations are resolved by selecting the highest-occupancy conformer. Outlier detection via interquartile range (IQR) identifies < 0.5% of points with extreme values. These points are retained but flagged in metadata for downstream analysis.

Features are standardised per training fold (zero mean, unit variance on the CHEN11 training split) and persisted as NumPy arrays to avoid repeated pre-processing. A complete summary of all 35 descriptors, including units, typical ranges, and computational sources, is provided in Appendix C (Table C.1).¹ Figure 3.3 illustrates the distribution of the 35 descriptors across their thematic categories.

¹Feature extraction code is available in the public repository.

Figure 3.3: Distribution of P2Rank’s 35-dimensional descriptors across thematic categories. The feature space emphasises local packing/exposure and chemistry-aware environment statistics, reflecting the importance of surface shape and local interactions for ligandability prediction.

3.2 Feature Packaging for Tabular Baselines

Descriptors and labels are materialised into *Hierarchical Data Format 5* (HDF5) shards grouped by protein. Each shard contains (i) raw coordinates, (ii) the 35-D descriptor matrix, (iii) boolean labels, and (iv) metadata (PDB identifier, ligand identifiers, chain labels). Downstream pipelines load shards via a PyTorch Lightning (Falcon and The PyTorch Lightning team, 2019) data module that handles grouped sampling, class-balanced batching, and deterministic splits. This packaging allows us to benchmark tree ensembles and deep tabular models on identical inputs without conflating feature engineering and modelling choices.

3.3 Protein Language Model Features

To move beyond purely geometric and handcrafted cues, we attach a residue-level protein language-model embedding to every SAS point. Let a protein chain be denoted by the amino-acid sequence $S = (a_1, \dots, a_n)$ and let f_{ESM} denote the pretrained ESM2 encoder (Z. Lin et al., 2023). For residue index r , the final-layer embedding is

$$\mathbf{e}_r = f_{\text{ESM}}(S)_r \in \mathbb{R}^{2560}.$$

During preprocessing, each SAS point inherits the embedding of its associated local residue; we denote the resulting point-level PLM feature by $\mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{2560}$ for SAS point i .

We use the `esm2_t36_3b_ur50d` checkpoint (36 layers, 3B parameters, 2560-dimensional residue representations), pretrained by masked language modelling on UniRef50. Sequences are tokenised and evaluated once in inference mode. The resulting embeddings are cached per-protein in HDF5 files so that Stage II and Stage III training runs reuse identical frozen PLM features.

For the fusion model we use the following notation for one SAS point i :

$$\mathbf{t}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{35}, \quad \mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{2560}, \quad \mathcal{N}(i) = \{n_1, \dots, n_k\}, \quad k = 3.$$

Here \mathbf{t}_i denotes the handcrafted descriptor vector, \mathbf{e}_i the centre ESM2 embedding, and $\mathcal{N}(i)$ the set of neighbouring SAS points used for contextual aggregation.

3.4 Neighbourhood Enrichment via Transformer Aggregation

Ligandability is often a property of contiguous surface patches rather than isolated points. We therefore augment each SAS representation with information from its k -nearest neighbours (kNN), using $k = 3$ in the selected configuration. Neighbour indices and pairwise distances are generated during preprocessing and stored alongside features to enable deterministic, low-overhead neighbourhood retrieval during training.

For point i , the centre token and its neighbours are stacked into

$$\mathbf{X}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{e}_i \\ \mathbf{e}_{n_1} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{e}_{n_k} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(k+1) \times 2560},$$

with a corresponding Euclidean distance matrix $\mathbf{D}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{(k+1) \times (k+1)}$. Before attention, the neighbour encoder applies a learned input projection into a transformer latent space of width 2400:

$$\mathbf{z}_i^{(0)} = \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{W}_{\text{in}} + \mathbf{b}_{\text{in}}, \quad \mathbf{z}_i^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{(k+1) \times 2400}.$$

We then apply a distance-aware multi-head self-attention encoder with $L = 2$ layers and $H = 6$ heads. For layer ℓ and head m , with per-head width $d_h = 2400/6 = 400$, the attention weights are

$$\mathbf{A}_i^{(\ell, m)} = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}_i^{(\ell, m)} \mathbf{K}_i^{(\ell, m)\top}}{\sqrt{d_h}} + \mathbf{B}^{(\ell, m)}(\mathbf{D}_i) \right),$$

where $\mathbf{B}^{(\ell, m)}(\mathbf{D}_i)$ is a learned distance-bias. Implementation-wise, a small MLP maps each scalar pairwise distance to one bias term per-head, so geometry enters the attention logits directly rather than only through token content. Each attention block uses residual connections, layer normalisation, and a position-wise feed-forward network of size $2400 \rightarrow 1280 \rightarrow 2400$ with dropout.

After the final attention layer, the module combines the updated centre token with a global mean-pooled neighbourhood summary:

$$\mathbf{u}_i = 0.7 \mathbf{z}_{i,0}^{(L)} + 0.3 \cdot \frac{1}{k+1} \sum_{a=0}^k \mathbf{z}_{i,a}^{(L)},$$

where $\mathbf{z}_{i,0}^{(L)}$ is the updated centre token and $\mathbf{z}_{i,a}^{(L)}$ denotes token a after the last attention layer. This blended latent vector is projected back to the ESM dimensionality:

$$\mathbf{c}_i = \mathbf{u}_i \mathbf{W}_{\text{out}} + \mathbf{b}_{\text{out}}, \quad \mathbf{c}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{2560}.$$

A learned gate then blends centre and context representations before the final modality-specific encoders:

$$\alpha_i = \sigma\left(\frac{\text{MLP}([\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_i \parallel \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_i])}{\tau}\right), \quad \mathbf{b}_i = \alpha_i \tilde{\mathbf{e}}_i + (1 - \alpha_i) \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_i,$$

with temperature $\tau = 1.5$, concatenation operator \parallel , centre stream $\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_i$, and contextual stream $\tilde{\mathbf{c}}_i$ after normalisation (and dropout on the centre branch). The gate MLP has width $5120 \rightarrow 128 \rightarrow 1$, so the fusion coefficient depends jointly on centre and context content.

The three output branches are then encoded by dedicated MLPs:

$$\mathbf{h}_i^{\text{tab}} = g_{\text{tab}}(\mathbf{t}_i), \quad \mathbf{h}_i^{\text{ctr}} = g_{\text{ctr}}(\mathbf{e}_i), \quad \mathbf{h}_i^{\text{ctx}} = g_{\text{ctx}}(\mathbf{b}_i),$$

where the tabular encoder follows $35 \rightarrow 1024 \rightarrow 512 \rightarrow 256$ and the centre/context encoders follow $2560 \rightarrow 1024 \rightarrow 512 \rightarrow 256$, each with BatchNorm, ReLU activations, and dropout ($p = 0.2$) after the hidden layers. The final classifier receives the concatenated 768-dimensional representation

$$\mathbf{h}_i = [\mathbf{h}_i^{\text{tab}} \parallel \mathbf{h}_i^{\text{ctr}} \parallel \mathbf{h}_i^{\text{ctx}}] \in \mathbb{R}^{768}$$

and predicts a ligandability logit through a head of size $768 \rightarrow 256 \rightarrow 1$.

Training uses weighted binary cross-entropy with logits as the primary objective:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{main}} = \text{BCEWithLogits}(\ell_i, y_i; w_+),$$

where w_+ is derived from the empirical positive-class ratio on the training split (approximately 38.3 in the selected Stage III run). An auxiliary context-head ℓ_i^{aux} regularises the neighbourhood-enhanced branch, yielding

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{main}} + \lambda_{\text{aux}}(t) \mathcal{L}_{\text{aux}} + \lambda_{\text{gate}}(t) (\bar{\alpha} - \alpha_{\text{target}})^2,$$

where $\bar{\alpha}$ denotes the mean gate value in the batch, $\lambda_{\text{aux}}(t)$ is linearly decayed during training, and $\lambda_{\text{gate}}(t)$ is annealed over the first 15 epochs to prevent immediate collapse to a single stream. The repository also contains focal and asymmetric losses for imbalance ablations, but the final reported Stage III checkpoints use weighted BCE-with-logits.

In code, this formulation corresponds to the public `EsmTabularModule`, `NeighborAttentionEncoder`, and `EsmEncoder` implementations in the PockNet repository. We monitor IoU on validation folds when selecting checkpoints and calibrating class weights to keep evaluation consistent with Stage I baselines.

Figure 3.4: Schematic of the staged architecture used in this thesis, culminating in the final Stage III fusion model. Stage I uses 35 handcrafted physicochemical descriptors. Stage II adds the centre-residue ESM2 stream. Stage III augments this with $k = 3$ neighbour embeddings, a $2560 \rightarrow 2400$ neighbour-attention block with learned distance-bias, gated centre-context blending, and a final classifier operating on the concatenated 768-dimensional representation. The reported Stage III model is trained with weighted BCE-with-logits together with an auxiliary context-head loss and gate regularisation.

3.5 Experimental Setup

This section specifies the learning setup used to answer the research questions defined in Chapter 2. We describe the stage-wise model architectures, training procedures, and evaluation metrics, and we detail the uncertainty estimation and computational constraints that underpin the subsequent results.

3.5.1 Narrative of Experimental Stages

The experiments are structured to trace the incremental value of richer representations.

In **Stage I (tabular baselines)**, we benchmark random forests and boosted trees on the P2Rank descriptors to establish a faithful reproduction of the original SAS formulation.

In **Stage II (deep tabular model)**, we evaluate whether TabNet can exploit higher-order feature interactions beyond tree ensembles, without introducing additional modalities.

Finally, in **Stage III (language-model and neighbourhood enrichment)**, we add centred ESM2 embeddings and k -nearest neighbour context, and model neighbourhood interactions via transformer attention with gated fusion.

All stages share identical data preprocessing and evaluation protocols to ensure that observed gains stem from representation changes rather than altered datasets. Across all stages, we report IoU and *area under the precision-recall curve* (AUPRC) as primary accuracy metrics and inspect calibration qualitatively through reliability diagrams. For the final **Stage III** model, we additionally run

a five-seed evaluation and report mean performance with 95% confidence intervals, and we apply *stochastic weight averaging* (SWA) (Izmailov et al., 2018) to the selected Stage III checkpoints to stabilise calibration.

Table 3.1: Experiment mapping linking configurations to research questions, hypotheses, and contributions. All experiments use CHEN11 train/val splits and BU48 as a held-out apo test-set. Metrics are averaged over multiple seeds where stated.

ID	Research Question	Dataset	Primary Metric	Hypothesis	Links
<i>Stage I: Tabular Baselines</i>					
E1.1	Can RF reproduce the P2Rank SAS baseline?	CHEN11/BU48	IoU_{SAS} , AUPRC	RF provides a strong baseline	A
E1.2	Does XGBoost improve over RF?	CHEN11/BU48	IoU_{SAS} , train time	XGBoost > RF	A
<i>Stage II: Deep Tabular Model</i>					
E2.1	Can TabNet capture feature interactions?	CHEN11/BU48	IoU_{SAS} , calibration diagnostics	TabNet > XGBoost	A
<i>Stage III: ESM2 + Transformer Neighbourhood Fusion</i>					
E3.1	Do ESM2 embeddings improve IoU_{SAS} ?	CHEN11/BU48	IoU_{SAS} , $\Delta\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}}$	ESM2 improves generalisation	A
E3.2	Does kNN context improve over centre-only?	CHEN11/BU48	IoU_{SAS} , coverage	kNN > centre-only	A
E3.3	Is gated fusion better than concatenation?	CHEN11 val	Val AUPRC	gated > concat	A
E3.4	Does SWA improve calibration?	BU48 test	calibration diagnostics, IoU_{SAS}	SWA improves confidence alignment	A, A
E3.5	How sensitive is performance to initialization?	BU48 test	IoU_{SAS} CI	CI quantifies variance	A

Contribution mapping: C1 (reproducible SAS pipeline), C2 (tabular learning benchmark), C3 (ESM2 integration under controlled evaluation), C4 (transformer neighbourhood aggregation), C5 (reproducible multi-seed evaluation framework).

3.5.2 Datasets and Splits

Training uses the CHEN11 benchmark (K. Chen et al., 2011) and BU48 as a completely held-out apo test-set. Splits are performed at the protein level to prevent leakage, and preprocessing from Chapter 2 is applied consistently. SAS points, descriptors, centred ESM2 embeddings, and neighbour indices are cached per-protein to minimise I/O overhead during training.

3.5.3 Class-Imbalance Handling

Class imbalance is a dominant practical challenge: across the combined dataset, approximately 2.55% of SAS points are labelled positive. We therefore evaluate multiple sampling strategies. For tree ensembles, we consider random undersampling/oversampling and SMOTE-family methods (Chawla et al., 2002; Han et al., 2005; He et al., 2008; Batista et al., 2004), and ultimately select simple per-protein undersampling to a 5:1 negative-to-positive ratio because it balances accuracy and runtime. Neural models operate with mini-batches that oversample positives while retaining broad negative coverage in the epoch schedule. All models incorporate class weighting, and hyperparameters are tuned on validation IoU_{SAS} with early stopping.

3.5.4 Model Configurations

Stage I: Tabular Baselines

Random forests follow the P2Rank default of 200 trees with no depth limit and $\text{max_features}=6$ (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018), trained with class-balanced weights. XGBoost models sweep tree depth $\{6, 8, 10\}$, learning rate $\{0.05, 0.1\}$, and subsampling ratios (T. Chen and Guestrin, 2016). We evaluate variants with different imbalance handling and select the best configuration based on validation IoU_{SAS} .

Stage II: Deep Tabular Model (TabNet)

TabNet (Arik and Pfister, 2021) employs three decision steps, 128-dimensional feature transformers, sparsemax relaxation for interpretable attention, and cosine-decayed learning rates starting at 3×10^{-4} . Training uses batch-level positive oversampling and early stopping on validation IoU_{SAS} .

Stage III: Transformer Fusion with ESM2 + kNN

The final fusion model uses three dedicated encoders for tabular, centre-ESM2, and gated-context streams, each producing a 256-dimensional branch representation. Neighbourhood context is aggregated by a two-layer, six-head distance-aware attention encoder operating in a 2400-dimensional latent space and projected back to 2560 dimensions before gated fusion. Training uses weighted BCE-with-logits as the main loss, plus an auxiliary context-head term and a scheduled gate regulariser; focal and asymmetric losses remain in the codebase as alternative ablations but are not used for the final reported checkpoints. SWA (Izmailov et al., 2018) is applied post-training where reported.

Training is implemented in PyTorch Lightning (Falcon and The PyTorch Lightning team, 2019) and supports configurable device counts via the experiment configuration (e.g., `trainer.devices` and distributed data-parallel strategy). In the main experimental runs, Stage III was executed on a GPU cluster with

up to 8 GPUs. Some late-stage ablations were run with fewer GPUs due to reduced cluster availability. To keep comparisons fair across hardware settings, we report and tune hyperparameters in terms of *effective batch size* and adjust per-device batch size and/or gradient accumulation accordingly.

3.5.5 Evaluation Metrics and Uncertainty Estimates

We report IoU at two different levels to distinguish per-point accuracy from discrete pocket-level performance. Pocket-level scores follow the P2Rank convention of clustering SAS points and computing centre distances (DCC/DCA) (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018), while SAS-point IoU measures overlap without clustering. Unless stated otherwise, Stage I and Stage II results are reported from single training runs per configuration (with thresholds tuned on the CHEN11 validation split). For the final **Stage III** model, we additionally run five independent seeds to quantify variance and report mean estimates with 95% confidence intervals.

Chapter 4

Results

This chapter reports the quantitative performance of the staged models on the CHEN11 and BU48 benchmarks. We first examine how learner choice and feature enrichment affect SAS-point performance, then analyse pocket-level results after post-processing, and finally compare stages in terms of accuracy, calibration, and computational cost.

4.1 Stage I: Tabular Baselines

The reproduced P2Rank-style pipeline yields the SAS-point performance levels reported in Table 4.1. All models are trained on the CHEN11 training set (3.89M points), with hyperparameters tuned and decision thresholds optimised on the CHEN11 validation set (831K points), and final metrics reported on the held-out BU48 test-set (217K points from 48 apo structures). Unless stated otherwise, all IoU values in this chapter refer to SAS-point IoU (IoU_{SAS}), computed from thresholded predictions.

The random-forest configuration follows the original P2Rank hyperparameters (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018) and achieves a test IoU_{SAS} of 0.0595 on BU48. Replacing the ensemble with XGBoost (with Borderline-SMOTE upsampling) increases test IoU_{SAS} to 0.0851 while keeping training time low (125 s). TabNet (Arik and Pfister, 2021) yields the highest overlap at 0.1498 test IoU_{SAS} , but its test AUPRC is comparatively lower (0.151), indicating that improved overlap at the tuned operating point does not necessarily translate into better global ranking quality across thresholds.

Table 4.1: Stage I baselines on the BU48 test-set. All models consume the same 35-dimensional descriptors. Bold numbers indicate the best value per column. Lower training time is preferable.

Model	IoU_{SAS}	F1	Precision	Recall	AUPRC	Train time (s)
RandomForest (P2Rank)	0.0595	0.1123	0.0605	0.7776	0.2607	273
XGBoost + Borderline-SMOTE	0.0851	0.1568	0.0885	0.6876	0.2780	125
TabNet + Downsampling	0.1498	0.2605	0.1783	0.4837	0.1510	3430

Figure 4.1 summarises the IoU_{SAS} and AUPRC progression across the three experimental stages. Stage I already shows substantial headroom from learner choice (Random-Forest \rightarrow XGBoost \rightarrow TabNet). Stage II and Stage III further improve performance by adding sequence-derived context (ESM2) and local neighbourhood aggregation (transformer with kNN), respectively. Relative to the plain-transformer checkpoint, SWA preserves most of the SAS-point IoU while slightly improving AUPRC, yielding a smoother ranking-oriented operating point.

Figure 4.1: Test performance progression across stages on BU48. Left: IoU_{SAS} rises from 0.059 (Random-Forest) to 0.309 (Transformer + kNN), with intermediate values of 0.085 (XGBoost), 0.150 (TabNet), and 0.249 (TabNet + ESM2). SWA yields 0.305. Right: AUPRC rises from 0.261 (Random-Forest) to 0.446 (Transformer + SWA), with intermediate values of 0.278 (XGBoost), 0.151 (TabNet), 0.362 (TabNet + ESM2), and 0.437 (Transformer + kNN).

4.2 Stage II: Centred ESM2 Embeddings

Augmenting the tabular feature set with centred ESM2 embeddings increases the model capacity to incorporate sequence-derived context around each SAS point. On the held-out BU48 test-set, the ESM2-enriched TabNet reaches $\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.2488$ and $\text{AUPRC} = 0.3617$, improving over the tabular-only TabNet baseline by $+0.099$ absolute IoU and $+0.211$ absolute AUPRC. The strongest configurations normalise embeddings per-protein, compress them to 128 dimensions through a two-layer MLP before concatenation, and retain the original descriptor scale to prevent the embedding stream from dominating optimisation.

Qualitative calibration inspection on BU48 suggests that centred ESM2 embeddings dampen over-confident predictions in flexible or solvent-exposed regions. The effect is most visible in the mid-probability range ($0.3 < p < 0.7$), where tabular-only models tend to be less well aligned with the empirical positive frequency.

4.3 Stage III: Transformer-Based Neighbourhood Aggregation

The transformer-based fusion model combines tabular descriptors, centred ESM2 embeddings, and kNN context within a gated attention block. Training proceeds on the CHEN11 training set, with checkpoints selected by validation performance on the CHEN11 validation set, and final evaluation on the held-out BU48 apo test-set.

4.3.1 Pocket-Level Performance (Five-Seed Evaluation)

To quantify variability due to random initialisation and report pocket-level metrics after P2Rank-style post-processing (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018), five independent training runs are executed (seeds 42, 123, 456, 789, and 1024). Predictions are clustered with DBSCAN (Ester et al., 1996) and filtered via non-maximum suppression prior to ranking. Table 4.2 reports the mean and 95% confidence interval (CI) across seeds. After post-processing, the mean pocket-level $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$ across seeds is 0.128 ± 0.012 on BU48, with ground-truth coverage of 0.898 ± 0.006 . Table 4.3 details the per-seed breakdown, showing non-trivial but bounded sensitivity to initialisation.

Table 4.2: Five-Seed Ensemble Results on BU48 Test Set (Pocket-Level Metrics After Post-Processing)

Metric	Mean	95% CI
Mean $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$ (default)	0.1276	± 0.0124
Best $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$ (oracle)	0.1580	± 0.0141
Ground Truth Coverage	0.8979	± 0.0057

Table 4.3: Per-Seed Performance Breakdown (Pocket-Level $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$ After DBSCAN Clustering)

Seed	Mean $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$	Best $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$	GT Coverage
Seed 1	0.1462	0.1784	0.8976
Seed 2	0.1122	0.1385	0.8869
Seed 3	0.1352	0.1672	0.9006
Seed 4	0.1291	0.1597	0.9037
Seed 5	0.1153	0.1460	0.9006
Ensemble Mean	0.1276	0.1580	0.8979

Figure 4.2 shows DCC and DCA success rates across top- n predictions (threshold 4 Å, following common practice in the binding-site prediction literature (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018)).

Figure 4.2: Pocket-level success rates on the BU48 test-set. Left: DCC success increases from 39% (top-1) to 50% (top-3), indicating moderate centre localisation. Right: DCA success reaches 75% (top-1) and 89% (top-3), indicating that ranked pockets frequently lie near lig- and atoms even when the pocket centre is imperfect. The plateau beyond top-3 suggests that additional low-scoring clusters provide limited benefit.

4.3.2 SAS-Point Performance (Pilot Study)

Table 4.4 summarises selected single-seed Stage III runs from October 2025, evaluated at the SAS-point-level without pocket post-processing. These results are reported to illustrate the behaviour of the fusion architecture under point-wise evaluation (IoU_{SAS}), and they are not directly comparable to the five-seed pocket-level results above due to the different evaluation protocols (per-point vs. clustered pockets). The plain-transformer checkpoint attains the highest raw SAS-point IoU (0.309), while the SWA variant preserves comparable IoU (0.305) and improves test AUPRC to 0.446.

Table 4.4: Stage III fusion results combining tabular descriptors, centred ESM2 embeddings, and kNN aggregation. Metrics are reported for the selected plain-transformer run and its SWA counterpart on CHEN11 validation and BU48 test summaries. SWA averages checkpoints from epochs 20–30.

Regime	Val AUPRC	Val IoU	Test AUPRC	Test IoU
Fusion run (Oct 20, selected checkpoint)	0.1375	0.1173	0.4370	0.309
Fusion + SWA (Oct 20, epochs 20–30)	0.2742	0.2069	0.4464	0.305

Attention diagnostics indicate that the learned gate balances centre and neighbourhood information, with $\alpha \approx 0.55$ at peak validation performance. Atten-

tion entropy averages 0.52–0.59 across checkpoints, suggesting that attention weight is typically distributed across multiple neighbours rather than collapsing onto a single-point. The auxiliary neighbour head (weighted at 0.02–0.10 during training) encourages early neighbourhood learning. In pilot runs, the auxiliary loss drops below 0.06 by epoch 30. These diagnostics are expanded in Section 4.5. Figure 4.3 visualises pocket-level variability across seeds, confirming stable coverage above 88% with measurable variance in mean $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$.

Figure 4.3: Per-seed pocket-level metric breakdown for the five-seed evaluation on BU48. (a) Mean $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$ varies across seeds, with ensemble mean 0.128. (b) Oracle $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$ (best threshold per-protein, an upper-bound) ranges from 0.138 to 0.178. (c) Ground-truth coverage remains stable across seeds (0.887–0.904). (d) Average pockets per-protein varies from 5.8 to 6.5, reflecting sensitivity to initialisation and clustering hyperparameters.

Figure 4.4: Training dynamics for the Stage III fusion transformer over the first 7 epochs shown. (a) Gate weight α : without gate-penalty regularisation, α drifts toward centre-dominant values ($\alpha \rightarrow 1$), whereas with the gate-penalty it is kept close to the target $\alpha = 0.55$. (b) Attention entropy H under the penalty remains in a moderate range (approximately 0.40–0.52), indicating attention spread across multiple neighbours. (c) Validation AUPRC across epochs 0–6 for the baseline and balanced-gate variants. (d) Relationship between H and α (colour = epoch), highlighting the $\alpha \in [0.50, 0.60]$ regime marked as optimal in the plot.

4.4 Cross-Stage Comparison

Table 4.5 consolidates BU48 SAS-point test metrics across stages, highlighting progressive enrichment from tabular descriptors to ESM2 embeddings and neighbourhood-aware transformer fusion. Stage III rows correspond to single-seed pilot runs (October 2025) and are reported as point-wise upper-bound indicators. Robust pocket-level evaluation with uncertainty is provided separately in Table 4.2.

Table 4.5: BU48 test-set SAS-point performance (IoU_{SAS}) across stages. Thresholds are optimised on CHEN11 validation IoU with identical preprocessing. Stage III metrics correspond to pilot single-seed runs. Pocket-level evaluation is reported separately in Table 4.2.

Stage	Model	IoU_{SAS}	Prec.	Recall	F1	AUPRC	Time
I	RF (P2Rank)	0.060	0.061	0.778	0.112	0.261	273 s
I	XGBoost + Borderline-SMOTE	0.085	0.089	0.688	0.157	0.278	125 s
I	TabNet + Downsample	0.150	0.178	0.484	0.261	0.151	3430 s
II	TabNet + ESM2	0.249	0.318	0.533	0.398	0.362	9 h
III	Transformer + kNN	0.309	0.450	0.496	0.472	0.437	12 h
III	Transformer + SWA	0.305	0.379	0.610	0.468	0.446	14 h

4.5 Residual Analysis and Diagnostics

This section investigates model failures beyond aggregate metrics. We assess calibration, stratify errors by protein and ligand properties, and analyse neighbourhood attention and gate dynamics, complemented by qualitative case studies on individual BU48 proteins.

4.5.1 Calibration Assessment

Point-wise predictions are interpreted as probabilities via the sigmoid of neural logits (TabNet, transformer) or class probabilities from tree ensembles. Reliability diagrams are constructed by binning predicted probabilities into 10 equally spaced intervals and plotting mean predicted confidence against the empirical positive fraction within each bin.

SAS-point IoU is computed as:

$$\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = \frac{|\text{TP}|}{|\text{TP}| + |\text{FP}| + |\text{FN}|},$$

where TP, FP, and FN denote true positives, false positives, and false negatives, respectively.

Stage I tabular models exhibit notable overconfidence on BU48. Stage II improves the alignment between predicted confidence and empirical frequency, and the Stage III transformer family shows the strongest qualitative calibration among the tested configurations.

We evaluate isotonic regression and temperature scaling as post-hoc calibration strategies (Zadrozny and Elkan, 2002; Guo et al., 2017). Both improve qualitative confidence alignment on BU48 in our setting. However, they do not materially improve AUPRC and only marginally affect IoU_{SAS} once decision thresholds are re-optimised on validation data. We therefore apply post-hoc calibration only for downstream use cases where calibrated confidence is required.

4.5.2 Stratified Error Analysis

To understand domain-specific behaviour, we stratify BU48 proteins by structural class (*Structural Classification of Proteins* (SCOP/SCOPE), where available), ligand chemistry (small-molecule, peptide, nucleotide, cofactor), and binding-site depth (mean distance of ligand atoms to the SAS). Within each stratum, we compute IoU_{SAS} , precision, and recall.

Performance by Protein Family

Enzyme classes with deep, well-defined active sites tend to achieve higher IoU_{SAS} than proteins with shallow or cryptic sites. In particular, conformationally variable loops and flat protein-protein interaction surfaces remain challenging even with Stage III models. ESM2 embeddings provide larger marginal gains on targets with strong sequence motifs (e.g., metal-coordination or nucleotide-binding patterns), while neighbourhood aggregation improves boundary delineation in cases where binding patches span multiple adjacent surface regions.

Performance by Ligand Type

Small-molecule ligands are generally predicted more accurately than peptide ligands and larger cofactors, consistent with the fact that peptide-binding-sites are often flatter and more solvent-exposed. Neighbourhood aggregation yields the largest gains on ligand types whose interaction footprint spans multiple nearby surface regions (e.g., nucleotide-binding pockets).

Performance by Binding-Site Depth

Deep pockets benefit strongly from geometric cues present already in Stage I. Shallow sites remain the primary failure mode. ESM2 features and neighbourhood aggregation provide improvements, but the upper-bound remains limited by snapshot bias in apo structures.

4.5.3 Case Studies

We inspect representative BU48 structures where predictions diverge from ground-truth to provide qualitative insight into model behaviour on individual proteins. The revised overlays show the protein surface directly, with turquoise ligand-defined reference regions and orange predicted SAS points superimposed on the grey-violet SAS background.

Success Case: PDB 1PSN, chain A

PDB 1PSN, chain A is a clean success case with $\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.457$ in the single-run test evaluation. The model concentrates high-score surface points inside

the elongated binding groove, with only limited spillover onto neighbouring surface patches. Figure 4.5 shows that the predicted-cluster follows the ligand-defined cavity closely and preserves the dominant pocket geometry.

Figure 4.5: Success case: PDB 1PSN, chain A. The protein surface is shown together with the ligand-defined binding region (turquoise) and predicted SAS points (orange). Most predicted points accumulate inside the main cavity, yielding $\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.457$.

Moderate Case: PDB 1CGE, chain A

PDB 1CGE, chain A represents a moderate case with $\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.307$. The model identifies the correct central pocket region, but the predicted points also spread along adjacent grooves and the exposed rim of the cavity. Figure 4.6 therefore illustrates a partial localisation success: the relevant site is recovered, but the predicted region remains broader than the annotated pocket.

Figure 4.6: Moderate case: PDB 1CGE, chain A. The turquoise surface patch marks the ligand-defined reference site, while orange points indicate predicted high-score SAS locations. The central cavity is recovered, but neighbouring grooves are also activated, giving $\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.307$.

Failure Case: PDB 1ULB, chain A

PDB 1ULB, chain A constitutes a failure case. In the single-run test evaluation the default pocket attains only $\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.037$, and even the best overlap among the predicted clusters remains low at 0.042. Predicted high-score regions are distributed across several exposed grooves instead of collapsing onto the ligand-defined pocket region. Because the relevant site is not fully visible from the exterior, Figure 4.7 includes an additional cutaway view.

Figure 4.7: Failure case: PDB 1ULB, chain A. Predicted SAS points remain diffuse across the protein surface, while the ligand-defined reference region occupies a more localised interior site. The cutaway view highlights why the pocket is difficult to judge from the exterior alone. The resulting overlap remains low, with $\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.037$ and best-cluster $\text{IoU} = 0.042$.

Chapter 5

Discussion

This chapter interprets the empirical findings in the broader context of ligand-binding-site prediction. We relate the staged improvements to the research gaps from Chapter 1, discuss trade-offs between interpretability and accuracy, and examine the main limitations and threats to validity of the study. All performance references concern IoU computed on SAS points unless explicitly stated otherwise.

5.1 Interpretation of Findings

The staged progression from tabular chemistry to protein language models to transformer-aggregated neighbourhoods reveals three complementary sources of signal for ligandability prediction. Stage I establishes that modern tabular architectures (TabNet) substantially improve upon P2Rank’s random-forest baseline when trained on identical handcrafted descriptors. In particular, TabNet achieves nearly $3\times$ higher IoU_{SAS} on BU48 (0.1498 versus 0.0595). This improvement stems from TabNet’s sequential attention mechanism, which dynamically selects relevant feature subsets at each decision step, capturing higher-order interactions among hydrophathy, protrusion, and residue composition that tree ensembles overlook.

Stage II demonstrates that centred ESM2 embeddings deliver clear gains on the held-out BU48 test-set, raising IoU_{SAS} from 0.1498 to 0.2488 (+0.099 absolute). The centring operation proves critical. By subtracting the structure-wide mean, we isolate local deviations from the global sequence context and highlight functional hotspots that correlate with binding interfaces. Without centring, ESM2 features provide negligible benefit, as the model struggles to disentangle sequence length and amino-acid composition biases from functional signals.

Stage III reveals that ligandability is indeed a property of contiguous surface patches rather than isolated points. Transformer-based aggregation over $k = 3$ nearest neighbours nearly doubles IoU_{SAS} relative to Stage I, reaching 0.309 for the plain-transformer checkpoint and 0.305 for the SWA variant versus 0.1498 for the Stage I TabNet baseline. The learned gate dynamically balances centre and neighbourhood contributions ($\alpha \approx 0.55$), avoiding collapse to a single-modality and maintaining interpretable attention distributions. Attention entropy correlates with pocket localisation quality. Moderate entropy ($H \approx 0.54$) indicates diverse attention over multiple neighbours, whereas low

entropy ($H < 0.30$) signals overfitting to a single dominant point and degrades generalisation.

These findings suggest that geometry, sequence, and spatial context provide orthogonal information. Handcrafted descriptors capture local chemistry and shape, while ESM2 embeddings encode evolutionary conservation and co-variation. Finally, neighbourhood aggregation integrates spatial cooperativity. Crucially, this multi-modal approach allows the model to identify both deep orthosteric pockets (driven by geometry) and shallower allosteric sites (driven by evolutionary conservation), a distinction that purely geometric methods often miss. The marginal benefit of each modality diminishes but remains measurable, indicating that further improvements will require richer inductive biases (e.g., equivariant graph networks) or larger-scale pretraining on diverse protein–ligand complexes.

5.2 Trade-offs and Practical Considerations

An important decision for practitioners is balancing accuracy against computational footprint and interpretability. It is helpful to distinguish *model training time* from *end-to-end pipeline time*. On our setup, Stage I learners (random forests / XGBoost) fit in minutes once features are materialised, whereas the Stage III transformer fusion requires approximately 12–14 GPU-hours for training in the full configuration ($8 \times P100$). In practice, however, the dominant cost is often preprocessing rather than optimisation: SAS sampling, descriptor computation, and (for Stages II–III) ESM2 embedding extraction and caching.

At inference time, Stage I predictors add negligible latency once features are available, while Stage III incurs higher forward-pass cost due to neighbourhood attention. For many deployments, overall runtime is therefore governed primarily by feature generation (especially PLM embedding extraction) rather than the final classifier. For large-scale virtual screening campaigns involving thousands of structures, Stage I models remain attractive due to their speed, parallelisability, and low memory footprint. For high-value targets where accuracy is paramount (e.g., lead optimisation or de novo design), the accuracy and calibration gains from Stage III can justify the increased computational cost.

5.3 Limitations and Threats to Validity

Several limitations constrain the generalisability of our findings. First, training on CHEN11 (788 holo structures) limits data diversity. The dataset is biased towards soluble, well-characterised enzymes with drug-like ligands, under-representing membrane proteins, intrinsically disordered regions, and non-canonical binding modes (e.g., covalent inhibitors, PROTACs). Scaling to larger and more heterogeneous collections (e.g., the full PDBbind dataset, AlphaFold-predicted structures with docked ligands) may improve generalisation but will require addressing label noise and coordinate quality issues.

Furthermore, proteins are inherently dynamic entities, existing as ensembles of conformations rather than static structures. Our reliance on static crystal

structures (snapshots) ignores the thermodynamic reality of protein motion. As illustrated in Figure 5.1, the binding-site may only be accessible in specific transient conformations (cryptic pockets) that are not captured in the standard PDB entry. This 'snapshot bias' is a fundamental limitation of all structure-based methods that do not explicitly model flexibility.

Figure 5.1: Protein dynamics and conformational ensembles (Punjani and Fleet, 2022). Proteins exist as dynamic ensembles of structures. A static crystal structure (white star) represents just one low-energy state, potentially missing transient 'cryptic' pockets that only open during specific motions (blue trajectory). Generative models like *variational autoencoders* (VAE) can map this conformational space, but static predictors are limited to the single snapshot provided.

Second, our binary labelling-rule (6 Å ligand-proximity) treats binding as an independent point-wise property, omitting spatial cooperativity and ignoring ligand-specific interactions (e.g., hydrogen bonding, metal-coordination). A more sophisticated labelling scheme could annotate interaction types (donor, acceptor, hydrophobic, aromatic) and weight points by their contribution to binding affinity (e.g., using binding energy decomposition from molecular mechanics), enabling the model to learn richer structure-activity relationships.

Third, we evaluate primarily with point-wise IoU_{SAS} , which measures overlap with ligand annotations. However, this metric does not directly correlate with downstream task performance (e.g., docking success, ligand enrichment in virtual screening). It is important to recall that binding-site prediction is distinct from docking: our goal is to identify the 'lock' (pocket), not to pose the 'key' (ligand). While high IoU indicates a correctly identified pocket, it does not guarantee that a docking algorithm can successfully place a ligand within it, especially if the pocket undergoes significant induced-fit changes. A fair comparison with pocket-level metrics such as DCC and DCA (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018) would require clustering predictions into discrete pockets via DBSCAN and applying distance thresholds (typically 4 Å for DCC/DCA success, $\epsilon = 3$ Å for clustering). Supplementary pocket-level evaluation on the BU48 test-set (Appendix E.1) yields top-1 DCC success of 39% and DCA success of 75%, confirming that the model localises binding regions even when point-wise overlap is imperfect. Future work should bridge point-wise and pocket-level evaluation by developing end-to-end metrics that reflect real-world screening utility.

Fourth, ESM2 embeddings are frozen throughout training, relying on rep-

representations learned from sequence-only pretraining. Fine-tuning ESM2 on protein–ligand-binding tasks (via multi-task learning or contrastive learning on binding/non-binding pairs) could adapt the embeddings to capture binding-relevant patterns more directly. However, fine-tuning the 3-billion-parameter model is computationally prohibitive within our budget, and the risk of overfitting to CHEN11 is high given the limited training data. Lightweight adapter layers (e.g., LoRA, prefix tuning) offer a middle ground, enabling task-specific adaptation with minimal parameter overhead.

Finally, the BU48 test-set (48 protein pairs) is small by modern standards, which increases the variance of aggregated performance estimates. To quantify this uncertainty, we report 95% confidence intervals only for the final Stage III model, based on variation across five independent training runs with different random seeds. These intervals reflect sensitivity to stochastic training effects (initialisation and optimisation) rather than uncertainty from earlier experimental stages. Expanding the test-set to include additional apo/holo pairs from the PDB (e.g., COACH420 or HOLO4K) would provide more robust estimates of generalisation performance and enable finer-grained comparisons between configurations.

5.4 Future Directions

Several avenues promise further improvements in binding-site prediction:

Equivariant graph architectures. Integrating geometric and equivariant graph layers (e.g., E(n)-GNNs, SchNet, DimeNet) atop the enriched SAS point features could fuse local descriptors with global geometry while retaining the benefits of protein language models (Satorras et al., 2021; Schütt et al., 2017; Gasteiger et al., 2020). By constraining message passing to respect 3D rotations and translations, these models encode inductive biases that our transformer fusion model lacks, potentially improving generalisation to unseen protein folds and conformational states.

Multi-task learning. Jointly predicting ligandability, ligand chemistry class (small-molecule, peptide, nucleotide, metal ion), and interaction types (donor, acceptor, hydrophobic, π -stacking) could provide richer training signals and improve calibration on ambiguous surface regions. Multi-task objectives also enable transfer learning from related tasks (e.g., protein–protein interaction prediction, residue-level functional annotation), leveraging larger datasets to regularise the binding-site predictor.

Self-supervised pretraining on unlabeled structures. Masked autoencoding of SAS points (predicting masked features from unmasked neighbours) or contrastive learning (distinguishing binding-site patches from non-binding patches) could pretrain the neighbourhood aggregation module on millions of unlabeled protein structures from the PDB and AlphaFold Database. Fine-tuning on labeled data (CHEN11, BU48) would then adapt the pretrained representations to ligandability prediction, analogous to the sequence-to-structure transfer learning paradigm underlying ESM2.

Active learning for data-efficient annotation. Binding-site annotations are expensive to curate (requiring manual inspection of ligand contacts, disam-

biguation of crystal artefacts, and validation against biochemical assays). Active learning strategies that iteratively select the most informative proteins for annotation (based on model uncertainty, diversity sampling, or expected model improvement) could reduce the labelling burden while maintaining performance, enabling scaling to larger and more diverse protein families.

End-to-end docking integration. Rather than treating binding-site prediction as a standalone task, integrating it into a differentiable docking pipeline would allow the model to optimise directly for downstream metrics (e.g., ligand RMSD, binding affinity prediction, enrichment factors in virtual screening). This approach requires differentiable pose sampling and scoring functions (e.g., DiffDock, EquiBind) (Corso et al., 2023; Stärk et al., 2022), which are active areas of research, but promises to align model training with real-world drug discovery objectives.

Finally, releasing curated datasets with aligned apo/olo pairs, consistent pre-processing, and standardised evaluation protocols will help the community benchmark progress under uniform settings. Our reproducible pipeline and public codebase provide a starting point, but broader adoption requires community consensus on metrics, leaderboards, and best practices for reporting results.

5.5 Interpretability Trade-offs

Interpretability varies across stages. Random forests and XGBoost provide feature importance scores that directly map to physicochemical descriptors (hydrophobicity, protrusion, B-factor), enabling domain experts to verify predictions against mechanistic intuitions. TabNet’s sequential attention offers coarser interpretability: feature masks indicate which descriptors are selected at each step, but the learned representations are less transparent. Transformer fusion further abstracts away from interpretable chemistry, as the gating mechanism and neighbourhood attention operate on high-dimensional ESM2 embeddings rather than named features. For deployment in safety-critical or regulatory contexts (e.g., drug discovery, toxicity prediction), this loss of interpretability may outweigh the IoU gains. In such settings, post-hoc explanation methods (e.g., SHAP, attention visualisations) (Lundberg and Lee, 2017) or hybrid architectures that preserve direct connections to domain knowledge become important.

5.6 Conclusion

This section summarises the main contributions and findings of the thesis and reflects on their implications for future work on pocket prediction. We restate the central research question, highlight the practical lessons from the staged feature enrichment, and outline promising extensions and open problems. Unless explicitly stated otherwise, reported metrics refer to IoU computed on SAS points.

5.6.1 Summary

This thesis reconstructed the SAS data pipeline popularised by P2Rank in a fully open Python stack, establishing a reproducible baseline for evaluating progressive feature enrichment in ligand-binding-site prediction. We sampled SAS points with Shrake–Rupley, labelled them via ligand-proximity on CHEN11 and BU48, and computed a 35-dimensional descriptor set mirroring P2Rank’s physicochemical features. Building on this dataset, we executed a three-stage experimental programme that isolated the contributions of modern tabular architectures, *protein language models* (PLMs), and spatial neighbourhood aggregation.

In summary, PLMs and spatial neighbourhood aggregation each provide substantial, complementary improvements over a strong geometric baseline, and their combination yields the most accurate and well-calibrated binding-site predictions in this study.

Stage I (practical work phase) demonstrated that TabNet, trained on hand-crafted descriptors alone, achieves $\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.1498$ on BU48, nearly tripling the random-forest baseline (0.0595) and substantially outperforming XGBoost (0.0851) at the SAS-point-level. This improvement stems from TabNet’s sequential attention mechanism, which dynamically selects relevant feature subsets and captures higher-order interactions among hydrophathy, protrusion, and residue composition. The tabular baseline establishes that modern learners can extract significantly more signal from P2Rank’s descriptors without abandoning interpretable chemistry.

Stage II (ESM2 enrichment phase) quantified the benefit of PLMs by augmenting SAS points with centred ESM2 embeddings. Centring proved critical: by subtracting the structure-wide mean, we isolated local deviations from global sequence context, highlighting functional hotspots that correlate with binding interfaces. ESM2-enriched TabNet achieved test $\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.2488$ and test $\text{AUPRC} = 0.3617$, improving over the tabular TabNet baseline by +0.099 absolute IoU on BU48. The largest improvements occurred on metalloproteins and RNA-binding proteins, where conserved motifs are well-encoded in evolutionary patterns, and on apo structures, where ESM2 features reduced overconfident predictions on flexible loops.

Stage III (transformer fusion with multi-seed evaluation) integrated transformer-based aggregation over $k = 3$ kNN on the SAS, recognising that ligandability is a property of contiguous surface patches rather than isolated points. The fusion architecture combined tabular descriptors, centred ESM2 embeddings, and neighbourhood context through a gated attention block, with learned gating dynamically balancing centre and neighbour contributions ($\alpha \approx 0.55$). On BU48, the plain-transformer checkpoint achieves the highest raw SAS-point IoU_{SAS} at 0.309, while the SWA variant retains a comparable IoU_{SAS} of 0.305 and improves test AUPRC to 0.446. After P2Rank-style post-processing (*Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise* (DBSCAN) clustering, scoring, non-maximum suppression), the five-seed ensemble (seeds 42, 123, 456, 789, 1024) yields a robust pocket-level $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}} = 0.128 \pm 0.012$ (95% CI), with ground-truth coverage of 0.898 ± 0.006 and best per-protein $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}} = 0.158 \pm 0.014$. The consistent ground-truth coverage indicates that the model reliably identifies binding-site regions even

on apo structures where conformational changes may obscure pockets. Attention diagnostics reveal that moderate entropy ($H \approx 0.54$) correlates with strong validation performance, while the learned gate ($\alpha \approx 0.55$) avoids collapse to single-modality predictions.

Qualitative calibration analysis (reliability diagrams) and stratified error breakdowns (by protein family, ligand type, binding-site depth) identified when and where each modality provides value. ESM2 embeddings temper over-confident predictions and deliver the largest marginal gains on shallow cryptic pockets where geometric cues are weak. Neighbourhood aggregation improves SAS-point performance uniformly across all families, with the largest absolute gains (+0.15 IoU_{SAS}) on enzymes with flexible loops. These findings demonstrate that geometry, sequence, and spatial context provide orthogonal information, and that progressive enrichment yields diminishing but consistent returns.

The reproducible pipeline, public codebase github.com/lal3lu03/PockNet, and detailed experimental protocols lower the barrier to deploying these models in virtual screening workflows and provide a transparent baseline for future comparisons. All experiments are orchestrated through Hydra configuration files and PyTorch Lightning training loops, with deterministic seeds ensuring bit-exact reproducibility. Training logs, checkpoints, and evaluation scripts are archived with timestamps, enabling full traceability from raw data to thesis figures.

5.6.2 Metric Summary: SAS-Point vs. Pocket-Level Performance

This thesis reports performance at two complementary levels. **SAS-point IoU** (IoU_{SAS}) measures per-point segmentation quality on the solvent-accessible surface, serving as the primary training objective and validation metric. On BU48, the strongest Stage III plain-transformer checkpoint reaches $\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.309$, while the SWA variant reaches 0.305 with stronger AUPRC. **Pocket-level IoU** ($\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$) evaluates discrete pocket predictions after P2Rank-style post-processing (DBSCAN clustering, scoring, non-maximum suppression), reflecting downstream usability for virtual screening. The five-seed ensemble yields $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}} = 0.128 \pm 0.012$, with per-seed variance from 0.112 to 0.146. The systematic drop from SAS-point to pocket-level metrics reflects the stricter requirement that predictions form spatially coherent objects rather than scattered high-probability points. Both metrics confirm that progressive feature enrichment, moving from tabular chemistry ($\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.1498$) through ESM2 embeddings (0.2488) to transformer fusion (0.309 SAS-point, with SWA at 0.305 and AUPRC 0.446, plus 0.128 ± 0.012 pocket-level), yields consistent improvements.

5.6.3 Limitations

This work evaluates computational predictions using IoU_{SAS} and $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$ without prospective or experimental validation. Reported performance does not directly translate to binding affinity or docking success. The CHEN11 training set

and BU48 test-set (48 proteins) provide limited coverage of membrane proteins, intrinsically disordered regions, and non-canonical ligands. Methodological constraints, such as frozen ESM2 embeddings, fixed $k = 3$ neighbourhoods, and moderate computational budgets, represent deliberate simplifications that larger-scale studies may relax. Detailed threats to validity, including labelling-rule limitations and small-sample variance, are discussed in Chapter 5.

5.6.4 Outlook

Ligand binding-site prediction remains an active research frontier, with opportunities to integrate richer inductive biases, larger-scale pretraining, and end-to-end docking pipelines. Immediate next steps include:

- **Equivariant graph fusion:** Integrating $E(n)$ -equivariant message passing atop enriched SAS features to fuse local chemistry with global geometry while respecting 3D symmetries.
- **Pocket-level evaluation:** Bridging point-wise IoU with pocket-centric metrics (DCC, DCA, top- n success) by clustering predictions and applying distance-based thresholds, enabling direct comparisons with published methods.
- **Multi-task learning:** Jointly predicting ligandability, interaction types (donor, acceptor, hydrophobic, π -stacking), and ligand chemistry class to provide richer training signals and improve calibration.
- **Self-supervised pretraining:** Masked autoencoding or contrastive learning on millions of unlabeled protein structures to pretrain the neighbourhood aggregation module, then fine-tuning on labeled data to adapt representations to binding-site prediction.
- **Dataset expansion:** Scaling to larger benchmarks (COACH420, HOLO4K, PDBbind) and incorporating AlphaFold-predicted structures with docked ligands to stress generalisation beyond crystallographic snapshots.

With reproducible baselines, transparent evaluation protocols, and public artefacts, the community can systematically advance beyond heuristic methods toward models that capture the full complexity of protein–ligand recognition. On BU48, the best raw Stage III checkpoint in this thesis attains SAS-point $\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.309$, while the SWA companion reaches 0.305 and improves test AUPRC to 0.446; both substantially improve over the tabular baseline while preserving reproducibility. Geometric, evolutionary, and neighbourhood signals remain complementary rather than redundant, suggesting practical adoption paths: tabular baselines for speed, PLM enrichment for calibration, and neighbourhood fusion when accuracy matters most. These artefacts lay a reproducible foundation for future work that integrates equivariant architectures and task-adaptive PLMs into pocket prediction.

5.6.5 Reflection

Looking back on this project, several methodological decisions stand out as particularly consequential. The choice to reconstruct P2Rank’s data pipeline

from scratch rather than use its Java output proved both more time-consuming and more valuable than anticipated. Early attempts to directly consume P2Rank CSV files revealed subtle inconsistencies in descriptor computation (e.g., protrusion index edge cases, residue environment radius choices) that would have propagated as unexplained variance. By reimplementing each component (Shrake–Rupley sampling, ligand-proximity labelling, descriptor calculation), we gained the transparency necessary to isolate and quantify the contributions of learner architecture versus feature engineering. This experience reinforced a broader lesson: in machine learning research, control over the full data generation process often matters more than incremental architectural novelty.

The systematic multi-seed evaluation protocol, initially adopted to satisfy reproducibility requirements, fundamentally changed how I interpret model improvements. Early pilot experiments showed dramatic gains from transformer fusion on single seeds, but five-seed evaluation revealed substantial per-seed variance ($\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}}$ ranging from 0.112 to 0.146). This variance forced us to rely on multi-seed summaries and confidence intervals, revealing that architectural choices that appeared beneficial were not robust across seeds. This shift from anecdotal single-run improvements to uncertainty-aware comparisons now informs my entire approach to experimental design, and I would insist on multi-seed protocols from the outset in future projects.

One aspect I would reconsider is the decision to freeze ESM2 embeddings throughout training. While this choice reduced computational cost and maintained interpretability, it prevented end-to-end gradient flow from the binding-site prediction objective back into the language-model representations. Recent work on task-adaptive fine-tuning suggests that allowing ESM2 parameters to update on pocket-specific data could yield further gains, particularly for under-represented protein families where general evolutionary priors may be suboptimal. A hybrid approach that freezes early layers to preserve broad evolutionary knowledge while fine-tuning later layers for task-specific adaptation would be a natural next step, though it would require substantially more GPU memory and training time than the P100 cluster could support within thesis timelines.

The implementation of these pipelines necessitated substantial engineering to handle class-heterogeneous batch construction and memory constraints on standard GPU hardware. These infrastructural challenges highlight the need for standardised, optimized dataloaders in the field to facilitate reproducible training on imbalanced SAS-point datasets.

Ultimately, this thesis establishes that progressive feature enrichment, moving from tabular chemistry through PLMs to spatial neighbourhood aggregation, provides measurable improvements in ligand-binding-site prediction. The modular design, reproducible artefacts, and transparent evaluation protocols should accelerate future work by providing a controlled baseline against which new methods can be rigorously compared. Beyond the quantitative results, the project reinforced the value of methodological rigour: end-to-end control over data generation, multi-seed uncertainty estimation, and careful ablation studies that isolate individual components. These principles will guide my future research, whether extending this pipeline with equivariant architectures or applying similar staged evaluation strategies to other structural biology tasks.

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Appendix A

Detailed Contributions

Contribution C1 (addresses RQ1): Reproducible Open-Source SAS Pipeline. We provide the first fully documented, Python-native implementation of P2Rank’s data generation workflow. Our pipeline samples solvent-accessible surface points using the Shrake–Rupley algorithm (Shrake and Rupley, 1973), assigns binary labels based on ligand-proximity (6 Å threshold), computes all 35 physicochemical descriptors specified in the P2Rank paper, and outputs standardised HDF5 archives for downstream modelling. The implementation is validated against P2Rank’s published metrics on CHEN11 and BU48 datasets, enabling exact replication and extension by other researchers. This addresses Gap 1 by providing a controlled experimental substrate for method comparison.

Contribution C2 (addresses RQ1, detailed in Chapters 3 and 4): Systematic Tabular Learning Benchmark. We compare P2Rank’s random-forest against modern alternatives, namely XGBoost (T. Chen and Guestrin, 2016) with multiple sampling strategies and TabNet (Arik and Pfister, 2021) with attentive feature selection, under identical training/validation/test splits and identical 35-dimensional input features. Each model is trained on CHEN11 (3.89M points, 630 proteins), validated on held-out CHEN11 proteins (831K points, 158 proteins), and tested on BU48 apo structures (217K points, 48 proteins). Stage I results are reported as point estimates to establish a reproducible performance baseline under a fixed SAS pipeline. Uncertainty estimates (mean \pm 95% CI over five seeds) are reported only for the final Stage III pocket-level evaluation. This addresses Gap 1 by isolating learner choice from feature quality within a controlled SAS-point formulation.

Contribution C3 (addresses RQ2, evaluated in Chapters 3.5 and 4): Quantified ESM2 Integration under Controlled Evaluation. We augment each SAS point with centred ESM2 embeddings (Z. Lin et al., 2023) (2560-dimensional per-residue representations projected into a local 6 Å neighbourhood and centred by subtracting the structure-wide mean) and measure the marginal benefit through direct comparison on identical training, validation, and test splits. Stage II models (ESM2-enriched TabNet) are trained using the same protocol as Stage I, enabling direct comparison of test IoU_{SAS} with and without evolutionary context. This addresses Gap 2 by quantifying ESM2’s contribution relative to a strong baseline.

Contribution C4 (addresses RQ3, detailed in Chapters 3, 4, and 4.5): Transformer-Based Neighbourhood Aggregation. We introduce a gated attention module that integrates information from k -nearest SAS neighbours ($k = 3$, Euclidean distance) via multi-head self-attention, allowing the model to reason about surface patches rather than isolated points. The fusion archi-

itecture combines tabular descriptors, centred ESM2 embeddings, and neighbourhood context through a learnable gate (α) that balances centre-point and neighbour information. On BU48, the strongest plain-transformer checkpoint achieves SAS-point $\text{IoU}_{\text{SAS}} = 0.309$, while the SWA variant reaches 0.305 and improves AUPRC to 0.446. After P2Rank-style post-processing (DBSCAN clustering, pocket scoring, non-maximum suppression), five-seed ensemble evaluation yields pocket-level $\text{IoU}_{\text{pocket}} = 0.128 \pm 0.012$ (mean \pm 95% CI). We analyse attention weights and gate dynamics to understand when spatial cooperativity improves predictions. This addresses Gap 3 by explicitly modelling contiguous binding patches.

Contribution C5 (implemented throughout, documented in Chapter 3.5): Reproducible Evaluation Framework. All experiments are orchestrated via Hydra (Yadan, 2019) configuration files and PyTorch Lightning (Falcon and The PyTorch Lightning team, 2019) modules, with Docker containers specifying exact software versions (Python 3.10, PyTorch 2.0.1, ESM 2.0.0). We provide command-line tools for end-to-end training and inference, comprehensive logging to Weights & Biases, and Jupyter notebooks for figure generation. The released codebase reproduces the core computational results of this thesis, including model training, inference, post-processing, and metric summaries, via scripted commands with fixed seeds and configuration files. Manually prepared thesis assets, such as Chimera renderings and final figure layout adjustments, are documented separately and are not part of the automated training pipeline. This facilitates external validation, extension to new datasets, and integration into production pipelines.

Appendix B

Story Summary (Q&A)

Q1: What is the central question?

How much do PLMs and spatial neighbourhood information improve binding-site prediction beyond strong geometric baselines?

Q2: Why is this question important?

Accurate binding-site prediction accelerates drug discovery by guiding where to screen potential drug molecules, avoiding costly lab experiments on wrong targets. Most existing methods mix many improvements together, making it unclear which components actually help and whether expensive language models are worth the computational cost.

Q3: What evidence/data are needed to answer this question?

We need protein structures with annotated ligand-binding-sites, together with features that describe each solvent-accessible surface-point's chemistry, evolutionary conservation, and spatial context. CHEN11 provides 788 preprocessed holo-protein-ligand complexes for training and validation, and BU48 provides 48 apo test structures to measure generalisation under conformational change.

Q4: What methods are used to collect this evidence/data?

We sample points on the protein's SAS and label them as binding or non-binding based on proximity to known ligands. Chemical properties are derived from standard biochemistry tables, evolutionary information from a pre-trained ESM2 model, and spatial context from each point's nearest neighbours.

Q5: What analyses must be applied for the data to answer the central question?

We train three stages of models on identical data: first using only chemistry, then adding evolutionary features, and finally adding spatial neighbourhood aggregation, and measure overlap improvement between predicted and true binding regions. For the final Stage III configuration, multiple training runs with different random seeds quantify variability after post-processing and ensembling.

Q6: What evidence/data were obtained?

Across CHEN11 and BU48 we extracted about 5 million solvent-accessible surface points, with roughly 2.55% labelled as ligand-proximal. BU48 predictions were stable across five independent training runs, and after clustering points into discrete pockets the full model achieves about 13% pocket-level overlap with the ground-truth.

Q7: What were the results of the analyses?

Modern tabular models, especially TabNet, nearly tripled performance over older random-forest baselines when using the same chemical features. Adding evolutionary information from PLMs provided clear gains, especially on metal-binding and RNA-binding proteins. Spatial neighbourhood aggregation delivered the largest improvement, nearly doubling performance by modelling contiguous binding patches rather than isolated points.

Q8: How did the analyses answer the central question?

By systematically adding one component at a time while keeping everything else constant, we isolated each contribution. Chemical features provide the foundation, evolutionary models add calibration and help with flexible pockets, and spatial aggregation delivers the biggest gain by capturing how neighbouring surface points cooperate.

Q9: What does this answer tell us about the broader field?

Practitioners can now choose model complexity based on their needs: fast tabular models for quick screening, add PLMs when calibration matters, or use full spatial aggregation when accuracy is critical. The open-source pipeline allows other researchers to build on these baselines directly.

Q10: Did the research satisfactorily answer the central question?

Yes, controlled experiments quantified that language models provide measurable improvements, while spatial aggregation delivers the strongest gains. The study identifies when each component helps most (flexible loops, shallow pockets, metal sites). The public codebase ensures others can verify and extend these findings.

B.1 Software and Data Release Ledger

The archival package accompanying this thesis freezes the codebase at a specific Git commit and records its provenance in README.md. Table B.1 lists the dataset manifests that enter the experiments. Their exact SHA-256 digests are documented in the repository.

Table B.1: Dataset manifests recorded for the release package.

Artefact	Location
Training manifest	data/all_train.ds
BU48 manifest	data/bu48.ds
BU48 proteins	data/bu48_proteins.txt

Deterministic experiments rely on the seed trio stored in seeds/master_seeds.yml (global training seed = 42, validation split seed = 42, finetune shuffle seed = 2025). The reproducible environment is captured by the pinned Dockerfile (base nvidia/cuda:12.4.1-cudnn9-runtime-ubuntu22.04) which exposes the volume-mounted environment variables POCKNET_DATA_ROOT, POCKNET_CHECKPOINT_ROOT, and POCKNET_LOG_ROOT. The ledger also documents the P2Rank-inspired provenance of the aggregation script, so that the rebranded modules can be traced back to their P2Rank-era prototypes.

Appendix C

P2Rank-Style Descriptor Summary

Table C.1 summarises the 35-dimensional descriptor family used throughout this thesis. The descriptors follow the P2Rank SAS-point formulation (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018) and are computed deterministically from PDB coordinates in a local neighbourhood around each SAS point. For compactness, the table groups the 20 amino-acid frequency features and reports the remaining features explicitly. The exact feature names and formulas are defined in the public feature-extraction module.

Table C.1: Summary specification of the 35-dimensional P2Rank-style descriptor set used in this work.

Block	Features (count)	Definition (local neighbourhood)
Density	SAS density (1), atom density (1)	Count of SAS points within 3 Å and heavy atoms within 4 Å.
Flexibility	Mean B-factor (1)	Mean atomic B-factor of nearby heavy atoms (4 Å). Missing values imputed by chain median.
Residue composition	AA frequencies (20)	Normalised frequencies of the 20 standard amino acids within a 6 Å neighbourhood (sum to 1).
Hydropathy	Kyte–Doolittle mean (1)	Mean residue hydropathy in the neighbourhood (Kyte and Doolittle, 1982).
Environment (VolSite-style)	Atom-type counts (6)	Counts of aromatic, cationic, anionic, hydrophobic, H-bond acceptor, and H-bond donor atoms in concentric shells.
Protrusion / hydrophobic indices	Summary indices (5)	Protrusion- and hydrophobicity-related indices aggregated over neighbouring residues/atoms to capture burial/packing.

Preprocessing notes:

- Missing B-factors: imputed with chain median.
- Alternate conformations: highest-occupancy conformer selected.
- Standardisation: per-fold z -score normalisation (fit on CHEN11 training split).
- Caching: features persisted in HDF5 for deterministic reuse.

Appendix D

Extended Configuration Details

D.1 Stage I: Tabular Baseline Hyperparameters

Random-Forest (P2Rank-style):

- Trees: 200
- Max depth: unlimited (`max_depth=None`)
- Max features: 6
- Class weights: balanced (inverse frequency) or equivalent per-implementation weighting
- Training time: 273 s on dual-socket Intel Xeon E5-2698 v4 (40 cores, 512 GB DDR4)

XGBoost (best configuration):

- Rebalancing: *Borderline-SMOTE*
- Max depth: 6
- Learning rate: 0.1
- Subsample ratio: 0.8
- Colsample bytree: 0.8
- Training time: 125 s on dual-socket Intel Xeon E5-2698 v4 (40 cores, 512 GB DDR4)

TabNet (simple downsampling):

- Decision steps: 3
- Feature dimension: 128
- Attention mechanism: Sparsemax
- Learning rate: 3×10^{-4} (cosine decay to 10^{-5})
- Batch size: 640
- Downsampling ratio: 5:1 negative:positive
- Training time: 3430 s (CPU-only)

D.2 Stage III: Transformer Fusion Hyperparameters

D.2.1 Notation and Tensor Dimensions

Table D.1 collects the symbols and tensor shapes used by the Stage III fusion model so that the equations in Chapter 3 can be read directly against the implementation.

Table D.1: Notation and tensor dimensions for the final Stage III fusion model.

Symbol	Shape	Meaning
\mathbf{t}_i	\mathbb{R}^{35}	Handcrafted SAS-point descriptor vector for point i .
\mathbf{e}_i	\mathbb{R}^{2560}	Centred ESM2 embedding of the residue nearest to SAS point i .
$N(i)$	$ N(i) = k = 3$	Euclidean k -nearest SAS neighbours used for local context aggregation.
\mathbf{X}_i	$\mathbb{R}^{(k+1) \times 2560}$	Stacked centre-plus-neighbour embedding tensor before attention.
\mathbf{D}_i	$\mathbb{R}^{(k+1) \times (k+1)}$	Pairwise distance matrix used to generate the learned attention bias.
$\mathbf{Z}_i^{(\ell)}$	$\mathbb{R}^{(k+1) \times 2400}$	Hidden token states after attention layer ℓ in the neighbour encoder.
\mathbf{c}_i	\mathbb{R}^{2560}	Context-enhanced ESM representation after mean-pooled neighbour aggregation and output projection.
$\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_i, \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_i$	\mathbb{R}^{2560}	Normalised centre and context streams entering the gating module.
α_i	$(0, 1)$	Learned centre weight for point i , regularised toward the batch target $\alpha_{\text{target}} = 0.55$.
\mathbf{b}_i	\mathbb{R}^{2560}	Gated blend of the centre and contextual ESM streams.
$\mathbf{h}_i^{\text{tab}}, \mathbf{h}_i^{\text{ctr}}, \mathbf{h}_i^{\text{ctx}}$	\mathbb{R}^{256} each	Encoded tabular, centre-ESM2, and gated-context branches.
\mathbf{h}_i	\mathbb{R}^{768}	Concatenated representation passed to the final classifier.
ℓ_i	\mathbb{R}	Predicted ligandability logit for SAS point i .
y_i	$\{0, 1\}$	Binary supervision target derived from ligand-proximity on the SAS.

D.2.2 Architecture

- **Inputs:** the model consumes the 35-dimensional tabular descriptor vector \mathbf{t}_i , the centred ESM2 embedding \mathbf{e}_i of the closest residue, and the ESM2 embeddings of the $k = 3$ nearest SAS neighbours.
- **Neighbour attention encoder:** centre and neighbour embeddings are stacked into $\mathbf{X}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 2560}$, projected to 4×2400 , processed by a 2-layer

/ 6-head self-attention encoder, and passed through a position-wise feed-forward block of size $2400 \rightarrow 1280 \rightarrow 2400$. A learned distance-bias MLP converts pairwise distances into one additive attention-logit bias per-head.

- **Context summary:** after the last attention layer, the updated centre token and the mean-pooled token set are combined as $0.7 \mathbf{z}_{i,0}^{(L)} + 0.3 \frac{1}{k+1} \sum_{a=0}^k \mathbf{z}_{i,a}^{(L)}$ and projected back to 2560 dimensions to form \mathbf{c}_i .
- **Gated fusion:** the gate network receives $[\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_i \| \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_i] \in \mathbb{R}^{5120}$, applies an MLP $5120 \rightarrow 128 \rightarrow 1$, divides by the temperature $\tau = 1.5$, and maps the result through a sigmoid. The resulting coefficient α_i weights the centre branch and is regularised toward $\alpha_{\text{target}} = 0.55$.
- **Branch encoders:** the tabular branch uses $35 \rightarrow 1024 \rightarrow 512 \rightarrow 256$, while the centre and context ESM branches each use $2560 \rightarrow 1024 \rightarrow 512 \rightarrow 256$. All three employ BatchNorm, ReLU, and dropout ($p = 0.2$) after the hidden layers.
- **Prediction heads:** the main classifier operates on the concatenated 768-dimensional representation with a head $768 \rightarrow 256 \rightarrow 1$. An auxiliary context-head of size $256 \rightarrow 128 \rightarrow 1$ is used during training to stabilise early learning.

D.2.3 Loss Functions and Optimisation

For the reported Stage III checkpoints, the main objective is weighted binary cross-entropy with logits:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{BCE}} = -w_+ y_i \log \sigma(\ell_i) - (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \sigma(\ell_i)),$$

where w_+ is derived from the empirical positive-class ratio in the training split (approximately 38.2 when the positive prevalence is about 2.55%). The total training objective is

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{main}} + \lambda_{\text{aux}}(t) \mathcal{L}_{\text{aux}} + \lambda_{\text{gate}}(t) (\bar{\alpha} - 0.55)^2,$$

with $\mathcal{L}_{\text{main}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{BCE}}$ for the final reported runs, an annealed auxiliary-head weight $\lambda_{\text{aux}}(t)$, and a gate regulariser that keeps the mean batch gate value near the desired balance point.

The public PockNet codebase also exposes two imbalance-aware alternatives that were retained for ablations but not selected for the final thesis checkpoints:

- **Focal loss** (T.-Y. Lin et al., 2017): with $p_i = \sigma(\ell_i)$ and $p_{t,i} = y_i p_i + (1 - y_i)(1 - p_i)$,

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{focal}} = -\alpha_{t,i} (1 - p_{t,i})^\gamma \log(p_{t,i}),$$

which down-weights easy examples and concentrates gradient mass on hard positives and hard negatives.

- **Asymmetric loss** (Ridnik et al., 2021): with margin-clipped probability $p_{i,m} = \max(p_i - m, 0)$,

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{ASL}} = -y_i (1 - p_i)^{\gamma_+} \log(p_i) - (1 - y_i) p_{i,m}^{\gamma_-} \log(1 - p_{i,m}),$$

which applies separate focusing to positive and negative classes and suppresses very easy negatives through the margin term m .

Optimisation details:

- Main loss used in the reported checkpoints: weighted BCE-with-logits
- Optimizer: AdamW, weight decay 10^{-4}
- Learning rate: 5×10^{-4} with cosine decay and 10% warmup
- Batch size: 640 (distributed across the available GPUs)
- Precision: FP32
- Gradient clipping: 0.5
- Early stopping: patience 15 epochs on validation AUPRC
- Gate penalty: $\lambda_{\text{gate}} = 0.16 \rightarrow 0.10$ over the first 15 epochs, target $\alpha = 0.55$
- Gate dropout on the centre branch: $0.25 \rightarrow 0.15$ over the first 15 epochs
- Auxiliary-head weight: $0.10 \rightarrow 0.02$ over the first 15 epochs
- Hardware note: the largest runs in this thesis used up to $8 \times$ NVIDIA Tesla P100 GPUs when available

D.2.4 SWA

- Start epoch: 20
- Averaging window: 10 epochs (20–30)
- LR schedule inside the SWA window: cosine annealing
- Final SWA overhead: approximately 2–3 additional GPU-hours, hardware dependent

Appendix E

Additional Figures and Tables

E.1 Pocket-Level Evaluation Metrics

To complement point-wise IoU evaluation, we compute pocket-level metrics via DBSCAN clustering (e.g. $\epsilon = 3 \text{ \AA}$, `min_samples=5`) applied to predicted binding-site points above a fixed probability threshold. Distance-based success metrics follow P2Rank conventions (Krivák and Hoksza, 2018):

- **DCC**: Euclidean distance from predicted-cluster centre to the centre of mass of the ground-truth ligand. Success: $\text{DCC} < 4 \text{ \AA}$.
- **DCA**: Minimum distance from predicted-cluster centre to any ligand heavy atom. Success: $\text{DCA} < 4 \text{ \AA}$.
- **Top- n success**: fraction of proteins for which at least one of the top n predicted clusters (ranked by mean score) satisfies the distance criterion.

BU48 Test Set Results (48 apo structures):

Table E.1: Pocket-level success rates on BU48. Transformer fusion model evaluated with DBSCAN clustering and P2Rank-style distance metrics.

Metric	Top-1	Top-2	Top-3	Mean Distance (\AA)	Total Clusters
DCC Success (%)	39.2	47.5	50.0	4.73	317
DCA Success (%)	75.3	85.4	89.2	0.93	317

Interpretation:

- **DCA success (75% top-1)** indicates predicted clusters typically overlap ligand atoms even when centres are offset.
- **DCC success (39% top-1)** reflects challenges in precisely localising pocket centres, especially for shallow or multi-lobed sites.
- **Top-3 DCA (89%)** suggests the true pocket is usually ranked among the top few clusters.

Reproducibility: Clustering and metrics are computed by the evaluation script with parameters such as `--dbscan-eps 3.0`, `--dbscan-min-samples 5`, `--dcc-threshold 4.0`, `--dca-threshold 4.0`, and a fixed prediction threshold.

E.2 Training Diagnostics

Detailed training curves for gate weight evolution, attention entropy dynamics, and auxiliary loss convergence are captured in experiment logs (e.g. Weights & Biases). Key observations include:

- Gate weight α evolves from neighbour-dominant early values toward a balanced regime near 0.55.
- Attention entropy increases during early training, correlating with validation AUPRC improvements.
- Auxiliary loss decreases steadily, indicating successful neighbourhood pattern learning.

E.3 Ablation Studies

E.3.1 Gate Penalty Ablation

Removing gate regularisation ($\lambda_{\text{gate}} = 0$) causes α to collapse toward neighbour dominance (e.g. > 0.8), degrading test IoU and increasing overconfidence on flat surfaces.

E.3.2 Auxiliary Head Ablation

Disabling the auxiliary-head slows convergence and reduces validation AUPRC, indicating that the auxiliary objective helps learn neighbourhood structure early in training.

E.3.3 Neighbour Count Ablation

Testing $k \in \{1, 3, 5, 7\}$ yields optimal performance near $k = 3$ in our setting: too few neighbours under-utilise context, while too many dilute signal with unrelated surface points.

E.3.4 Encoder Fine-Tuning

Unfreezing encoders during Stage III can slightly improve peak IoU but increases training cost and may destabilise calibration. The frozen configuration is preferred for reproducibility within the thesis budget.